

Partition Function with Particles-Antiparticles And Role of Rest Mass

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Traditionally, the fermion partition function is obtained using the grand canonical approach even without particle-antiparticles production (e.g. electron-positron pairs). Thus, one imposes an $\langle N \rangle$ and allows for all N (number of particles) using a weight function $\exp(uN/T)$, where u is the chemical potential and T temperature. If T is high enough for pair production, the grand canonical scheme is retained, but $\langle N \rangle$ represents the “excess” of electrons i.e. N electrons - N positrons. The electrons and positrons are treated as independent fermion gases with $u(\text{electron}) = -u(\text{positron})$ being the link that pairs are produced or annihilated. This approach assumes completely independent N (electron) and N (positron) numbers, which is an approximation. The same approach may be applied to a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas (relativistic or nonrelativistic (1)) with pair production. In such a case, a “grand canonical partition function” $\sum_{N_1, N_2} Q(N_1) Q(N_2) \exp(u/T (N_1 - N_2))$ is employed to obtain results consistent with the fermion approach. Here $Q(N_1)$ and $Q(N_2)$ are canonical MB partition functions for N_1 or N_2 particles.

In (2), it is shown an issue arises when calculating particle number fluctuations. If the grand canonical partition function approach is used with N_1 and N_2 being independent, then fluctuation calculations may differ by a factor of 2 over a canonical approach in which $N_1 = N_2$ is imposed. Thus, it seems that there is a significant issue at play.

In this note, we consider the Maxwell-Boltzmann case as a starting point (so one does not need to carry over from the Fermi-Dirac picture). We argue that the factor $\exp(uN/T)$ used as a weight in grand canonical partition function calculations is related to maximum uncertainty in N , the number of pairs, in a system in an ensemble subject to a constraint on the sum of N related to $2mc^2$, the minimum energy lost through pair creation. We argue this by analogy with the calculation of $\exp(-E/T)$ as the canonical weight. Thus, we try to suggest that for a Maxwell-Boltzmann case which requires no chemical potential, one may use: $\sum_{N_1} Q(N_0 + N_1) Q(N_1) \exp(-uN_1/T)$. This yields usual results if $u_1 = 2mc^2$. In particular, we wish to show that even though the usual weight $\exp(u/T (N_1 - N_2))$ leads to $\exp(u/T (N_0))$ (where N_0 is the low temperature number of electrons if the number of positrons and extra electrons are equal, there is still a damping $\exp(-2mc^2 N/T)$ due to pair creation. This is implicitly included in relativistic calculations, but seems to be added in an ad hoc manner to nonrelativistic ones.

Fermion Approach to Electron-Positron Pairs

In (2), it is argued that if a system has a temperature T and a chemical potential “ u ”, one has the following usual result for the electrons:

$$\langle N_0 \rangle + \langle N_1 \rangle = \sum_{N_1} e^{-N_1/[1 + \exp((e-u)/T)]} \quad ((2))$$

The positrons are argued to be negative energy electrons with the distribution: $1 -$ electron distribution for negative e . Thus:

$$\langle N_1 \rangle = \sum_{-e} \frac{1}{1 + \exp((e-u)/T)} = \sum_{-e} \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-(e-u)/T)} = \sum_{e} \frac{1}{1 + \exp((e+u)/T)} \quad ((3))$$

Thus, the positrons have $-u$ as a chemical potential and the electrons u . One may note this approach does not seem to force equal numbers of positrons and electrons. A grand canonical approach is used for the electrons and positrons independently.

Equal and Opposite Sign Chemical Potentials for Particles and Antiparticles

In the above, electrons and positrons have equal magnitude, but opposite sign, chemical potentials. In (4), a general argument is provided for this. Consider two independent probability functions $Q(N_1)Q(N_2)$ where N_1 represents particles and N_2 antiparticles. $Q_1 = \sum_{e_i} \exp(e_i/T)$ for the MB case. It is suggested that should maximize $\exp(\ln(Q(N_1)) + \ln(Q(N_2)))$ where an increase in N_2 of 1 forces an increase in N_1 of 1 (i.e. a pair is created). Thus, maximizing the exponent:

$$\ln(Q(N_1+1)) - \ln(Q(N_1)) + \ln(Q(N_2+1)) - \ln(Q(N_2)) = 0 \text{ yields } u_{\text{particle}} = -u_{\text{antiparticle}} \quad ((4))$$

In this note, we wish to show that although u and $-u$ represent chemical potentials, the idea that there no damping weight factor for the number of pairs produced does not seem to be the case. There seems to be a weight related to $\exp(-2mc^2/T)$, but this is already contained in $\exp(-e/T)$ where e is relativistic energy. In the nonrelativistic case, it is not included and must be added manually unless one brings $\exp(-u_1 N_2/T)$ to account for a maximum uncertainty in the number of pairs produced subject to a constraint $u_1 = 2mc^2$ that each pair uses up a minimum amount of energy of $2mc^2$.

Fluctuation Issues

In the above, it is seen that a grand canonical approach to both the electrons and positrons does not strictly ensure that N_2 positrons implies $N_0 + N_2$ electrons (N_0 being the low temperature number of electrons). In (2), two partition functions are evaluated for the relativistic Maxwell-Boltzmann case, the grand canonical and the canonical. The partition functions are given as:

$$\text{Grand canonical: } ((5)) \quad \sum_{N_1, N_2} (z)^{N_1} (z)^{N_2} / [N_1! N_2!]$$

$$\text{Canonical: } ((6)) \quad \sum_{N_1, N_2} \delta(N_1 - N_2) (z)^{N_1} (z)^{N_2} / [N_1! N_2!]$$

It should be noted that no chemical potential is used as the authors note in order that average charge be 0 i.e. $u=0$. (Even if there were a chemical potential, it would disappear in the canonical approach because uN_1 and $-uN_2$ for electrons and positrons cancel with $N_1=N_2$.)

It should also be noted that the relativistic approach used means the single particle partition function is $\exp(-e/T)$ where $e = \sqrt{p^2 + m_0^2 c^4}$. Thus, for Q^N in the nonrelativistic limit there is a damping factor of $\exp(-2N mc^2/T)$. Thus there is a damping due to extra particle-antiparticle pairs which is not directly associated with the chemical potential. Here the 2 comes from an mc^2 for both an electron and positron.

The delta function is written in a form of $\delta(x) = \int dx \exp(ikx)$ and a closed form with a modified Bessel function obtained. (See (2) for full details.)

It seems the canonical approach strictly enforces the idea that an electron-positron pair contains one particle and one antiparticle. Yet, when number fluctuations are calculated a difference of up to factor 2 results (see (2)). This seems to be significant, as number fluctuations should be physical. Thus, it seems a number of nonphysical terms are included in the grand canonical approach and this has a strong effect on the fluctuation calculation.

Maximizing Uncertainty of Pair Number

The usual approach taken in particle-antiparticle cases is to use a grand canonical partition function which applies to: $N = N_{\text{electron}} - N_{\text{positron}}$. For the Fermi-Dirac case, which already uses the grand canonical approach at low temperatures, this seems to be natural. Thus, the grand canonical weights apply to "extra electrons" N . The physical situation is that $N_{\text{electron}} = N_0 + N_{\text{positron}}$, but N_{electron} and N_{positron} are allowed to fluctuate independently with the only restriction being that u applies to electrons and $-u$ to positrons. Thus, it seems this is only an approximation which includes a significant amount of unrealistic terms. When carried over into a Maxwell-Boltzmann calculation (1), the same grand canonical idea is used i.e.:

$$\text{Sum over } N_1, N_2 \quad Q(N_1)Q(N_2) \exp((N_1 - N_2)u/T)$$

Where N_1 represents electrons and N_2 positrons. In the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, however, there is no reason to use a "grand canonical approach" applied to "excess" particles. Imagine, for the sake of argument, one has particles-antiparticles which are described completely in the Maxwell-Boltzmann scheme. In such a case, any particle antiparticle fluctuations are due directly to pair production or annihilation. Thus, we argue that N_2 , the number of pairs is the important variable.

Consider the canonical case with a weight factor of $\exp(-E/T)$. This arises from considering many systems in an ensemble. The number of systems is M and the total energy E_0M . Then, $\exp(-E_i/T) = m_i$ is the solution of an m_i which maximizes the number of arrangements (or uncertainty) of:

$$M! \prod_i m_i! \quad ((7))$$

Here m_i is the number of systems in an ensemble with the energy E_i and there is a constraint $\sum m_i E_i = MU$ where U is the average energy.

In this note, we ask how one would maximize the uncertainty in the number of particles-antiparticles present, instead of using immediately $\exp(-(N_1-N_2)u/T)$ from the grand canonical scheme.

Let m_i be the number of systems with N_i positrons in the ensemble. Then one wishes to maximize:

$$M! / \left[\text{Product over } i \text{ } m_i! \right] \quad ((8))$$

The question is whether there is any constraint? If there is no constraint, then $m_i = \text{constant}$, i.e. all numbers of pairs of particles-antiparticles have the same weight i.e. the same probability of occurring. (In the literature, constraints are usually applied to conserved quantities such as energy or $N_1 - N_2 = \text{excess electrons}$.) This seems to be consistent with the approach used in the literature, i.e. $\exp(-(N_1 - N_2)u/T)$ with $N_1 = N_2$ and yields their results. If the chemical potential is negative for electrons, it is positive for positrons and $N_1 - N_2$ cancel regardless of the value of N_2 . The problem is that for the nonrelativistic case (1), one has to add $2mc^2$ in an ad hoc fashion.

It seems, however, that there is a constraint on pair production as each pair requires a minimum of $2mc^2$ of energy and so a weight factor of $\exp(-u_1 N_2)$ where N_2 is the number of positrons is suggested. For example, for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, one would have:

Sum over N_2 $Q(N_0 + N_2) Q(N_2) \exp(-u_1 N_2)$ as a partition function

$$= \text{Sum over } N_2 \exp[-1/T (A(N_0 + N_2) + A(N_2) - u_1 N_2)] \quad ((9))$$

(Note: For the MB gas, $Q(N)$ contains a $1/N!$, so it drops for as N increases.)

Here $A(N)$ is free energy and u_1 is negative.

Maximizing the exponent would yield (for a nonrelativistic MB gas):

$$kT \ln [L^3 (N_0 + N_2)/V] + kT \ln [L^3 (N_2)/V] - u_1 = 0 \quad ((10))$$

If $u_1 = 2mc^2$, one obtains the grand canonical results of (1).

One may ask whether there should be a damping as more particle-antiparticle pairs are produced. Both the canonical and grand canonical schemes of ((5)) and ((6)) with no chemical potential present implicitly contain such a damping factor which is $\exp(-2mc^2/T)$ in the nonrelativistic limit. Thus, ((10)) would be consistent with ((6)) for $u_1 = 2mc^2$. Thus, simply considering chemical potential seems to be a little misleading as $\exp(-uN_2/T) \exp(uN_2/T) = 1$, i.e. there is no effect due to changing the number of particles and antiparticles. There is an effect due to mc^2 i.e. $\exp(-2mc^2/T)$. This seems to be in keeping with the following picture.

Consider a microcanonical approach without pair production. One has N particles with a total energy of E . Particles are correlated through E and so if one particle contains most of E , the others contain almost no energy. This scenario appears rarely compared to other scenarios of energy distribution, with each scenario having a weight of 1. If one has many particle-antiparticle pairs forming in a microcanonical system, temperature should go down because much energy is depleted creating the rest masses. Thus, there is little to distribute and this scenario (although having a weight of 1) appears less frequently than others for which there is more energy available to distribute. Thus, attempting to maximize the number of pairs subject to a constraint does not seem unreasonable.

Consider the case of (1) in which a grand canonical approach is used:

$$\text{Sum over } N_1, N_2 \quad Q(N_1) Q(N_2) \exp(- (N_1-N_2)u/T)$$

Here $N_1=N_0+N_2$ and so the term with the chemical potential should not really contribute anything. If one is only interested in a maximum, the above is rewritten as:

$$\exp(\ln(Q(N_1))) \exp(\ln(Q(N_2))) \exp(- (N_1-N_2)u/T) = \exp(A(N_1)/T + A(N_2)/T - u/T (N_1-N_2)) \quad ((11))$$

$$A(N_1)=-kT \ln(Q(N_1))$$

Maximizing leads to: $d/dN_1 A(N_1) = u$ ((12a)) and $d/dN_2 A(N_2) = -u$ ((12b)), but the author of (1) inserts an mc^2 on the LHS of both ((12a)) and ((12b)). If one adds ((12a)) and ((12b)), u disappears, but one has an extra $2mc^2$ term. Thus, one could have removed $u/T(N_1-N_2)$ and added a damping factor of $\exp(-2mc^2/T N_2)$ and obtained the result of ((12a)) plus ((12b)). Given that the number of electrons is N_0+N_2 and the number of positrons N_2 , with N_2 varying, it is not necessarily surprising that ((11)) is not a good approximation for number fluctuations as shown in (2). For the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, it is not clear why one would use the grand canonical approach of ((11)) when the canonical, which is more accurate, although still an approximation, may be calculated analytically.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it may appear that by using chemical potentials of u and $-u$ for electrons and positrons, that each scenario of N_i pairs has the same weight i.e. $\exp(u/T (N_0+N_2)) \exp(-u/T N_2) = \exp(uN_0/T)$ where N_0 is the excess number of electrons. This, however, does not seem to be the case, because each pair depletes $2mc^2$ amount of energy leading to an extra factor of $\exp(-2mc^2/T)$. For a relativistic calculation (e.g. relativistic Maxwell-Boltzmann etc), this mass term is automatically included because e in $\exp(-e/T)$ includes rest mass. It seems that given the large T involved for pair production, one would automatically choose the relativistic case, but the nonrelativistic approach still appears in the literature e.g. (1).

For the nonrelativistic approach, $2mc^2$ is not included and may be manually added in a somewhat ad hoc manner as in (1). Alternatively, one argue that maximizing the uncertainty in the number of pairs i.e. $M! / [\text{Product over } i \text{ } m_i!]$ with a constraint on m_i 's related to rest mass

energy being used also yields $\exp(-2mc^2/T)$ factor and shows there is a damping weight related to the number of pairs. It seems good to be aware of this maximization of pair uncertainty as it appears to be implicitly contained in a relativistic approach of partition functions. Furthermore, given that chemical potentials of u and $-u$ are associated with electrons and positrons and that $N_{\text{electron}} = N_0 + N_2$ and $N_{\text{positron}} = N_2$, with N_2 varying, it seems the fugacity product makes no impact as $u^{N_2} \cdot (-u)^{N_2} = 0$.

References

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